

H2020-FNR-2020-2 Project no. 101000560

Rapid discovery and development of enzymes for novel and greener consumer products

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 01-06-2021

Duration: 4 years

D6.3 – Mid-set of market research dossiers.

Work Package N°:	6
Deliverable N°:	6.7
Lead Beneficiary:	SUSMOM
Other participants:	
Version:	1.0
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Dissemination level:	Public
Due date:	Month 24

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101000560

Different compounds and markets are intended to be targeted at RADICALZ. D6.7 (M24) provides an overview of the molecules, segments, and discusses the state-of-the-art of the research lines after two years of project. Proof-of-principles have been reached at laboratory scale, useful enzymes (and variants) have been identified, a patent application has been filed (see D6.5), and some industrial partners have been contacted to explore exploitation options. Overall, applications of the consortium can be divided in two main areas, one related to “bulk” applications, and another one comprising uses as nutraceuticals or food additives. In all cases, bio-based substrates are employed, with the aim to maximize the environmental profile of the applications.

- Bulk applications. Establishment of synthetic procedures to produce known and new surfactants, thickeners or emulsifiers, with new marketable properties; and use of newly identified and designed enzymes to remove polymeric fibers from industrial effluents.

- Nutraceuticals and food applications. Generation of novel products with use in food industry, with options for “food-grade” labelling (opening new markets). Production of compounds with applications as antioxidants, anti-inflammatory or as pharmaceutical compounds (a patent application has been filed, see D6.5).

Overall, during the first two years of RADICALZ efforts have been put on identifying new enzymes and tailoring them for the specific applications. Process optimizations will be reached during the second part of the project. In some cases contacts with external stakeholders have been already established, to explore the options for a future knowledge transfer (or IP licensing). The patentability of the other research lines is currently until consideration / development (see D6.5).

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